

OpenCitations, an open e-infrastructure to foster maximum reuse of citation data

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Note

Lightning talks should be submitted as a 1-page proposal (approximately 500 words). Please fill out the name, postal address and email address of the corresponding author in the footer below, and add the author information using the table above. Each cell should contain one author name and one affiliation. Please delete unused rows, or copy and paste rows to include more authors.

If your proposal is accepted, you will be invited to give a 10-minute presentation at IDCC. For further details, please see: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc22>

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URL: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc22>

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Text of your lightning talk proposal

OpenCitations (<http://opencitations.net>) is an independent not-for-profit infrastructure organization for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data by the use of Semantic Web (Linked Data) technologies, and fully espouses Open Science and the FAIR principles. Moreover, these are also of central relevance to data reuse within the scope of the EC-funded project OpenAIRE, which advances Open Science and provides a platform whereby a large-scale collection of research outputs is easily discoverable and re-usable. OpenCitations is involved in the OpenAIRE-Nexus project to create an e-infrastructure to assist publishing research “for the benefit of the open science community worldwide”. Since, by definition of the UNESCO Recommendations of Open Science, science practice is “open” if it makes “scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society”, re-usability is one of the main foci of OpenCitations, whose citation data satisfies all the Reuse guidelines provided by FAIR in terms of richness, provenance, usage licenses and domain-relevant community standards.

In detail, a) OpenCitations data comprise a domain-agnostic scope of coverage (1.2 billion citations as of January 2022) which is currently approaching parity with that of the main proprietary citation indices; b) every data object in OpenCitations is accompanied by machine-readable provenance metadata recording its source, the nature of any subsequent curatorial modification or correction, the dates of such actions, and the identities of the agents involved (whether human or computational); c) to ensure the greatest possible reusability, all OpenCitations data are published under a Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Waiver that permits downloading and re-use of any nature; and d) OpenCitations activities adopt Semantic Web technologies, particularly the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and the Web Ontology Language (OWL). The generic OpenCitations Data Model is used to structure all OpenCitations RDF data, facilitating the semantic interoperability with related data from other providers of open scholarly information. In addition, our open source software, used to run all our databases and services, not only permits third parties to re-use our developments but also ensures that the OpenCitations system can be re-created elsewhere in the unlikely event that OpenCitations itself ceases to operate, thereby ensuring the preservation and longevity of our work and data. In conclusion, OpenCitations provides an example of a successful open e-infrastructure in which the reusability of data is integral to its mission, namely “to make global scholarly citation data available at zero cost and without restriction for third party analysis and reuse, in both human- and machine-readable formats”.